

Coordinated State Estimation and Control of Water and Power Systems Via Nonlinear Moving Horizon Estimation and Predictive Control

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Coupled Water-Energy Systems

Water side

- Pressure Service Constraints.
- Storage as a Buffer.
- Operational Limits. [1]

Water-energy Nexus

- Energy-Water Trade-off.
- Operational Synergy.
- Integrated Modeling. [2]

Energy side

- Power Flow Dynamics.
- Variable Energy Pricing.
- Grid Stability. [3]

Proposed Method

Proposed Framework

- Acknowledge that not all the states are measured in the real-world water-energy nexus. [4]
- Strategically chosen sensor locations to ensure observability. [5]
- Coordinated state estimation and predictive control.
 - Ensure statistically consistent state estimation via MHE that guarantees recursive feasibility for the coordinated MPC.
 - Ensure optimal water and power flow (OWPF).
 - Handle the non-linearities of the coupled PDS-WDS.

Integrated System Modeling

Hydraulic Model

(1) Hydraulic Mass Balance:

$$D_i = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i} Q_{ji}^{in} - \sum_{k \in \mathcal{N}_i} Q_{ik}^{out} \quad (1)$$

(2) Tank Dynamics:

$$h_{T,i}(k+1) = h_{T,i}(k) + \frac{T_s}{A_{T,i}} \left(Q_i^{in}(k) - Q_i^{out}(k) \right) \quad (2)$$

(3) Tank Limits:

$$h_{T,i}^{min} \leq h_{T,i} \leq h_{T,i}^{max} \quad (3)$$

(4) Head Loss (Pipe friction):

$$h_{ni} - h_j = R_{ij} \cdot Q_{ij} \cdot |Q_{ij}|^{0.852} \quad (4)$$

(5) Pump Head Curve:

$$h_p = u_p(A - B \cdot Q_p^c) \quad (5)$$

Power Flow Model

(1) AC Nodal Power Balance (Injection Form):

$$P_i^{dev} = P_i^{net}(V, \theta), \quad \forall i \in \{1, 2\}, \quad (6)$$

$$Q_i^{dev} = Q_i^{net}(V, \theta), \quad \forall i \in \{1, 2\}, \quad (7)$$

$$P_i^{net}(V, \theta) = \sum_{j=1}^N |V_i| |V_j| \left(G_{ij} \cos(\theta_i - \theta_j) + B_{ij} \sin(\theta_i - \theta_j) \right), \quad (8)$$

$$Q_i^{net}(V, \theta) = \sum_{j=1}^N |V_i| |V_j| \left(G_{ij} \sin(\theta_i - \theta_j) - B_{ij} \cos(\theta_i - \theta_j) \right). \quad (9)$$

(2) Device-Side Net Injections:

$$P_1^{dev} = P_{Grid} + P_{PV} + P_{B1} - P_{L1} - P_{Pump3}, \quad (10)$$

$$P_2^{dev} = P_{DS} + P_{WT} + P_{B2} - P_{L2} - P_{Pump1} - P_{Pump2}, \quad (11)$$

$$Q_1^{dev} = Q_{Grid} + Q_{PV} + Q_{B1} - Q_{L1}, \quad (12)$$

$$Q_2^{dev} = Q_{DS} + Q_{WT} + Q_{B2} - Q_{L2}. \quad (13)$$

Moving Horizon Estimation (MHE) Formulation

Estimation Objective

(1) Optimization Problem (Past Window N_e):

$$\hat{x}_k = \arg \min_x \left(\|x - f(\hat{x}_{k-1}, u_{k-1})\|_{Q^{-1}}^2 + \|y_k - g(x)\|_{R^{-1}}^2 \right) \quad (14)$$

(2) System Constraints:

$$\hat{x}_{k+1} = f(\hat{x}_k, u_k, \hat{w}_k) \quad (15)$$

$$h_T^{min} \leq \hat{h}_{T,i} \leq h_T^{max} \quad (16)$$

$$y_k = g(\hat{x}_k, z_k) + v_k = \mathbf{C}x_k + v_k \quad (17)$$

where \mathbf{C} is a selection matrix defined by the sensor placement. [6]

- **States measured:** Tank levels (h_5, h_6) and Battery SoC (SoC_1, SoC_2).
- **States unmeasured:** Nodal total heads (H_5, H_6).

Tuning & Integration

(3) Process Noise Covariance (Q):

$$Q = \begin{bmatrix} Q_{\text{tank}}\mathbf{I}_2 & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & Q_{\text{pres}}\mathbf{I}_2 & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & Q_{\text{SoC}}\mathbf{I}_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (18)$$

(4) Measurement Noise Covariance (R):

$$R = \text{diag}(R_{h_{T1}}, R_{h_{T2}}, R_{SoC_1}, R_{SoC_2}) \quad (19)$$

(5) MHE-MPC Link:

- Full state reconstruction at step k :

$$\hat{x}_k \implies \text{Initial state for MPC}$$

MPC Setup and Cost Function

States:

$$x_k := [\text{SoC}_k \ h_k^T]^\top, \quad (\text{BESS state-of-charge, tank level}) \quad (20)$$

Control inputs:

$$u_k := [q_{p,1,k} \ q_{p,2,k} \ q_{p,3,k} \ P_{\text{DS},k} \ P_{\text{Grid},k} \ P_{\text{B1},k} \ P_{\text{B2},k} \ Q_{\text{DS},k} \ Q_{\text{Grid},k}]^\top \quad (21)$$

Disturbance:

$$w_k := [q_{1,k}^{\text{dem}} \ q_{2,k}^{\text{dem}} \ P_{\text{PV},k} \ P_{\text{WT},k} \ P_{\text{L1},k} \ P_{\text{L2},k} \ Q_{\text{L1},k} \ Q_{\text{L2},k} \ Q_{\text{PV},k} \ Q_{\text{WT},k}]^\top \quad (22)$$

Algebraic decision variables:

$$z_k := [|V_{1,k}| \ |V_{2,k}| \ \delta_{1,k} \ \delta_{2,k} \ \mathbf{h}_k]^\top, \quad (23)$$

(bus magnitudes/angles \Rightarrow nodal pressure heads, non-manipulated but optimized)

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\substack{\{u_{k+\ell}, z_{k+\ell}\}_{\ell=0}^{N_p-1} \\ x_{k+N_p}}} & \sum_{\ell=0}^{N_p-1} \left(\underbrace{\lambda_{k+\ell} P_{\text{Grid},k+\ell}}_{\text{grid cost}} + \underbrace{c_{\text{DS}}(P_{\text{DS},k+\ell})}_{\text{diesel cost}} + \underbrace{\lambda_{k+\ell} P_{\text{pump},k+\ell}}_{\text{pump energy}} + \underbrace{c_{\text{B}}(P_{\text{B1},k+\ell}, P_{\text{B2},k+\ell})}_{\text{battery cycling}} \right) \Delta t \\ & + \alpha_{\text{switch}} \underbrace{\sum_{\ell=0}^{N_p-1} q_{p,1,k+\ell} q_{p,2,k+\ell}}_{\text{pump switching penalty}} + \underbrace{\rho_e e_{k+\ell}}_{\text{slack}} + \rho_V \underbrace{\sum_{i \in \{1,2\}} (|V_{i,k+\ell}| - V_i^{\text{nom}})^2}_{\text{voltage regularization}} \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

s.t.

$$\text{Prediction Model} \quad (25)$$

$$\text{Physical boundaries} \quad (26)$$

$$\text{System constraints} \quad (27)$$

State Estimation Results

— Ground Truth - - - MHE Estimate ◆ Raw Measurement

MPC Results

References

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